
Managerial Planning Model For Enhancing Company Performance

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze and determine the effect of external environmental factors, organizational factors, organizational culture, and strategic planning on the company performance of employees of PT Wika Realty. The method used is quantitative research with a causal model and data analysis techniques using the SmartPLS 3.0 application. Primary data was collected by distributing online questionnaires to employees with managerial positions involved in strategic planning and decision-making with a tenure of more than five years at PT Wika Realty, totaling 100 employees with a sample size of 80 respondents. The results of this study are statistically supported, namely that there is a direct positive and significant influence on strategic planning and company performance on external environmental factors, managerial factors, and organizational culture.

1. Introduction

Businesses have an environment of constant turbulence. Digitalization also takes on its role in the changes that occur. Not over with upheaval and digitalization, a destructive situation is now engulfing companies worldwide. Brosseau and Thaker (2019) stated that the things experienced by the company were accelerating and at a point that did not yet exist. The current destructive situation brought about by the global COVID-19 pandemic is just an extreme example. Today companies no longer enjoy the luxury of developing strategies for several year intervals, but companies are struggling to find a survival plan for the next quarter or month (Blackburn & Schneider, 2020).

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The pandemic crisis causes the impact of changes still being discussed in Indonesia today. In 2020, the capital market on the Indonesia Stock Exchange experienced uncertain conditions since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. From the beginning of the year to the end of 2020, the effects of construction companies tend to be negative, as experienced by PT Waskita Karya (-30%), PT Wijaya Karya (-19%), and PT. Housing Development or PTPP (-13%) and PT Adhi Karya (-6%). The effect is not yet at the original point and can be seen from the graph below;

Picture1.Trends of BUMN Construction Stocks 2020
Source: Yahoo Finance (2020)

The decline in stock prices will certainly have an impact on company profits. Quoted from Big Alpha (2020), BUMN profits in the construction sector, namely Wijaya Karya (WIKA), Adhi Karya (ADHI), and Housing Development (PTPP), experienced a decline of 90% in mid-2020 compared to mid-2019. Wijaya Karya's income decreased by 96% (IDR 50 billion compared to IDR 1.35 T); Housing development income decreased by 94% (IDR 26.36 billion compared to IDR 519.23 billion); Adhi Karya's income decreased by 95% (IDR 15.38 billion compared to IDR 351.22 billion); even Waskita lost (lost IDR 2.6 trillion compared to IDR 1.5 T).

One of the companies whose performance has been hampered due to the COVID-19 pandemic is Wijaya Karya (WIKA). Quoted in *Bisnis.com* (2020) that PT. Wijaya Karya, during the pandemic, experienced some work that was not clear. The same thing was quoted on the page *NBC* (2021), where the state-owned construction company, namely PT. Wijaya Karya during 2020, the company's performance declined. Corporate net income decreased to IDR 185.76 billion at the end of 2020, equivalent to 92% annually.

Researchers are interested in following up on the strategic management implemented by WIKA in maintaining its existence so that it can overcome the impact of the covid-19 pandemic even though it has experienced a significant profit reduction, namely 92% of net profit the previous year. The unprecedented pandemic crisis has pushed many organizations, including WIKA, to be in a state of urgency towards innovation, for example, changing business objectives, products, materials, etc.(Bello & Libarikian, 2020).

Although WIKA REALTY is predicted to help WIKA overcome the Covid-19 pandemic crisis, WIKA REALTY has not yet achieved its maximum performance. Corporations in carrying out their business always have goals for them; in achieving these goals, qualified company performance is an effort to get maximum income. (Jannah & Ajmal, 2022).

The step taken by WIKA to improve WIKA REALTY's performance is by injecting capital. The injection of capital until the establishment of a holding hotel will certainly impact the company's performance. This step is expected to improve the company's performance, especially in increasing profits. The strategy implemented by WIKA REALTY to improve its performance is known as Diversification. Diversification is a strategy by a corporation to enlarge its business by opening new business units, either from the same business or different ones. The company's value can be formed following the thinking of the capital market, namely by Diversification (Arte & Larimo, 2022).

Multidivisional companies that are not small generally have three strategic scales: corporate, business, and function. The diversification strategy is part of the corporate strategy(Pertiwi & Suhartini, 2022). Therefore, this study will take the Strategic Planning variable to see its effect on company performance. The selection of strategic planning variables is based on the results of research conducted by Amoo & Mahtab (2022), AlQershi (2021), and(George & Monsters, 2019). Additionally, the researcher considers the selection of strategic planning to be broader than just focusing on diversification variables. This strategic planning variable is expected to produce better implications for the company.

Following up on this, of course, WIKA REALTY needs to develop an improvement strategy, especially in producing the best company performance to survive these challenges and not be replaced by its competitors. This description becomes the basis for the researcher to choose other independent variables for improving the performance of WIKA REALTY. The variables that the researcher chooses are external environmental factors on company performance.

Companies will be able to win a business competition if there is managerial ability to implement a strategy that is able to overcome competition in the long term. Especially WIKA REALTY is implementing a diversification program, namely hotel holding, which requires managerial skills in allocating company resources. Not only that, but the leader must also have the authority so that the program can run optimally. Considering that the main shareholder of WIKA REALTY is the parent company of WIKA, a synergy between the parent company and WIKA REALTY is needed for the program to run well. Therefore, managers must develop programs that can benefit both parties.

Talking about the hotel holding program, a crucial problem experienced by the company is the changing work culture. In simple terms, activities that are carried out repeatedly by employees in a company, and it has been agreed that these habits are mandatory, are called work culture. The expansion of the program from realty services to hotel holding services certainly results in changes in several aspects, including job descriptions. Therefore, the creation of a new habit, although this change can be said to be not much different from the previous job description, there are things that are different from the employee's work pattern. For this reason, the work culture of researchers is used as an independent variable in determining the performance of WIKA REALTY.

Strategic planning, external, and managerial factors affect organizational performance (Haryanto, 2019). However, there is still limited research that uses strategic planning as an intervening variable to mediate external environmental and managerial factors' influence on corporate performance. In accordance with research, Aris Mardiyono (2013) concluded that external business factors, and managerial factors, have an impact on strategic planning to support corporate performance in MSME actors for the city of Semarang. In preparing a strategic plan, the managerial side needs to consider and evaluate the external environmental factors and, of course, the internal capabilities of the company represented by managerial factors. These conditions and factors influence each other and influence the decision-making process in strategic plans and policies to manage the company (Mardiyono, 2013). This is the background of researchers making strategic planning an intervening variable.

Research conducted by Mediaty (2010) shows that strategic climate, habits, and strategic planning are jointly related to performance, while the strategic environment affects performance but does not affect strategic planning. Suwono (2018) research showed a non-negative influence between strategic planning and performance. Aram and Cowen (1991), as a result of their research, revealed that strategic plans have no relationship to performance.

Currently, there is quite a lot of research regarding the relationship between strategic, managerial, and performance planning. However, the difference from previous research is the addition of variables: the culture of acting with independence and strategic planning acting on intervening and the corporate sector. There are still very few studies using the corporate sector conducted by researchers. According to the description above, the theme of this research is "Manager Planning Model in Improving Company Performance at PT Wika Realty."

2. Materials and Methods

According to Sugiama (2008) method is a theory to design a real symbol. Suppose it is in accordance with Sugiono (2007). In that case, it is a scientific method to obtain the correct data set, which aims to obtain findings, develop and prove so that in time it can be useful for understanding, solving, and anticipating problems. The research method is quantitative. Quantitative research emphasizes more on theory testing and is measured through research variables. This research uses a measuring instrument, a questionnaire distributed to WIKA Realty.

The survey is a research method that will be used in this research. The descriptive and expurgatorial research type was chosen for the approach, a method used was a descriptive survey. This method was used because this research was carried out by entering directly into the field with a questionnaire. This research uses a causal model because there are independent and dependent variables. This research entirely uses primary data for all variables, namely the external environment (X1), managerial (X2), strategic plan (X3) organizational performance (Y). The analysis technique carried out in this research is the Partial Least Square (PLS) testing method. The previous research is slightly the same as the current research in the variables. The causal method is used as a path analysis to test the hypotheses in this research. The model analysis technique uses SEM, which operates with the SMART PLS 3.0 program.

3. Results and Discussions

Hypothesis Testing

After performing the PLS algorithm and bootstrap using SmartPLS 3.0, hypothesis testing can be carried out to assess whether the hypothesis after submission is supported or not. The researcher tested the hypothesis by measuring the direct effect, which looked at the path coefficient number and the indirect relationship to see the relationship between the intervening variables in the research.

1) Direct Effect

Table 1. Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Means (M)	Standards Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O /STDEV)	P Value
Corporate Culture -> Company Performance	0.285	0.286	0.103	2,780	0.006
Organizational Culture -> Strategic Planning	0.341	0.336	0.114	3,003	0.003
External Environmental Factors -> Company Performance	0.233	0.234	0.102	2,276	0.023
External Environmental Factors -> Strategic Planning	0.468	0.473	0.110	4,256	0.000
Managerial Factors -> Company Performance	0.103	0.105	0.098	2.050	0.029
Managerial Factors -> Strategic Planning	0.185	0.184	0.078	2,366	0.018
Strategic Planning -> Company Performance	0.376	0.373	0.099	3,787	0.000

Source: processing used SmartPLS 3.0 (2022)

H1: The Effect of External Environmental Factors on Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.468 on external environmental factors to strategic planning. This means that there is a positive influence on the external environmental factor variables on the strategic planning variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value of 4.256 and p-value of 0.000 (<0.05) mean that external environmental factors have a significant direct effect on strategic planning.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H2: Managerial Relations in the Strategic Plan

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients, the table above shows the original sample number of 0.185 on managerial factors to strategic planning. This means that there is a positive influence on the managerial factor variable on the strategic plan variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 2,366, and the p-value is 0.018 (< 0.05), which means that managerial factors are directly related to strategic planning. Therefore, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

H3: The Influence of Organizational Culture on Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the table above, the original sample number is 0.341 for organizational culture to strategic planning. This means a relationship exists between the organizational culture variable and the strategic planning variable. Instead, it also shows the t statistics of 3.003 and p values of 0.003 (< 0.05), which means that corporate culture is directly related to strategic planning. Therefore, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

H4: Effect of External Environmental Factors on Company Performance

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients, the table above shows the original sample number of 0.233 on external environmental factors to company performance. These data indicate a relationship between the external environmental variables and the company's performance variables. In addition, it also shows a t statistic of 2.276 and a value of 0.023 (< 0.05), which means that external factors are directly related to organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

H5: The Effect of Managerial Factors on Company Performance

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients, the table above shows the original sample number of 0.103 on managerial factors to company performance. The data shows a relationship between managerial factors and company performance variables. In addition, it also shows the t statistics of 2.050 and a value of 0.029 (< 0.05), which means that managerial factors are directly related to organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

H6: The Influence of Corporate Culture on Company Performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above shows the original sample number of 0.285 on organizational culture to company performance. This means that there is a relationship between the company's climate variables and the company's performance variables. In

addition, it also shows the t statistics of 2s,780, and the values of 0.006 ($< 0s,05$), which means that organizational culture is directly related to organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

H7: The Effect of Strategic Planning on Company Performance

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, the table above shows the original sample value of 0.376 in strategic planning to company performance. This means that there is a positive influence on the strategic planning variable on the company's performance variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 3.787, and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that strategic planning has a significant direct effect on company performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this research is accepted and statistically supported by these results.

Table 2. Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STD EV)	P Value
Organizational Culture -> Company Performance	0.128	0.125	0.054	2,379	0.018
External Environmental Factors -> Company Performance	0.176	0.177	0.068	2,586	0.010
Managerial Factors -> Company Performance	0.070	0.067	0.033	2,136	0.033

Source: processing used SmartPLS 3.0 (2022)

H8: The Influence of External Environmental Factors on Company Performance is Mediated by Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the table, the external environmental factor variables are related to the company's performance, with strategic planning acting as a mediator between the two. The original number of the relationship between the three variables is 0.176, which means that there is a positive influence in the external environment relationship on organizational performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the t statistic is 2.586, and the p values are 0.010 (< 0.05), which means that the external environmental factor variables are indirectly related to the company's performance with strategic planning that acts as a mediator. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis in this research is accepted and supported statistically by the results of this research.

H9: Effect of Managerial Factors on Company Performance Mediated by Strategic Plans

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the table, managerial factor variables are related to company performance with strategic planning, which acts as a mediator between the two. The original value of the relationship between the three variables is 0.070, which means there is a positive influence on managerial influence on organizational performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the t statistics is 2.136, and the p-value is 0.033 (< 0.05), which means that managerial factor variables are indirectly related to organizational performance and strategic plans that act as mediators. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis in this research is accepted and supported statistically by the results of this research.

H10: The Influence of Corporate Culture on Organizational Performance is mediated by Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the table, the organizational culture variable on the company's performance with strategic planning acts as a mediator between the two. The original value of the relationship between the three variables is 0.128, which means that there is a good relationship between the influence of company behavior on company performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2,379, and the p-value is 0.018 (< 0.05), which means that the corporate culture variable is indirectly related to the company's performance, with strategic planning acting as a mediator. Therefore, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis in this research is accepted and supported statistically by the results of this research.

Discussion***H1: The Effect of External Environmental Factors on Strategic Planning***

The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.468 on external environmental factors to the strategic plan. This means that there is a positive relationship between the external environment on the strategic plan variable. In addition, it also shows the t statistics of 4,256 and values as big as 0,000 (< 0.05), which means that external environmental factors are directly related to strategic planning.

The external environment influences the strategic plan, where the external environment is an external condition, and its influence has an impact on the life and development of the organization. The environment has a role in the company's lifetime because the environment decides the strategy that will be carried out. The company's strategy is increasingly determined by environmental forces inside and outside the company (Wardani et al., 2016). Based on this description, the results of the research are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Sijabat (2016) and Haryanto (2019).

H2: The Effect of Managerial Factors on Strategic Planning

The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows that the original sample value is 0.185 on managerial factors to strategic plans. This means a positive relationship exists between the external environment and the strategic plan variable. In addition, it also shows the t statistics of 2,366 include values of 0.018 (< 0.05) which means that the factors directly affect strategic planning.

The intensity of the strategic plan depends on managerial factors, such as the manager's expertise and confidence in strategic planning. Management as planning must have certain competencies to carry out strategic plans, namely managerial skills and other knowledge to see opportunities that appear (Sijabat, 2016). Based on the description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Sijabat (2016) and Haryanto (2019).

H3: The Influence of Organizational Culture on Strategic Planning

The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.341 on organizational culture to strategic planning. This means a positive relationship exists between the organizational culture variable and the strategic planning variable. The t statistics value also shows this of 3,003 as well as values of 0.003 (< 0.05) which means that corporate culture is directly related to strategic planning. Based on this description, the results of the research are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Mulyadi (2001) and Govindarajan (2001).

H4: Effect of External Environmental Factors on Company Performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows that the original sample value is 0.233 on external environmental factors to the company's performance. This means that there is a positive relationship between external environmental variables on company performance variables. In addition, it also shows the t statistics value of 2,276 and values as big as 0.023 (< 0.05), which means that external environmental factors are directly related to company performance.

External environmental factors influence companies to force companies to take appropriate actions and manage their sustainable development. This will influence companies to improve the sustainability of their products and operations by reducing costs, improving quality, managing risk, and gaining a social image through competitive advantage. Opportunities, threats, and changing environments from external factors will encourage organizations to operate efficiently and effectively and improve their performance. (Wahab et al., 2019). Based on the description, the research results are following the results of research conducted by Mulyadi (2001) and Govindarajan (2001).

H5: Effect of Managerial Factors on Organizational Performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows that the original sample number is 0, 103 on managerial factors to company performance. This means if there is a positive relationship between the managerial factor variable and the firm's performance variable.

In addition, it also shows the t statistics value of 2 050 and *values* as big as 0.029(<0.05), which means that managerial factors are directly related to company performance.

The managerial factors that need to be mastered include controlling the company's processes. So, with that, managers can determine the range of company performance results they will get (Haryanto, 2019). The strategic plan cycle is seen in managerial factors, one of which is personal manager (Wardani et al., 2016). Based on the description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Wardani et al. (2016).

H6: The Influence of Corporate Culture on Company Performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.285 on company behavior to company performance. This means that there is a positive relationship between the company's behavior variable on the organizational performance variable. In addition, it also shows the t statistics value of 2,780 and *values* as big as 0.006(< 0.05), which means that organizational culture is directly related to organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the results of this study well accept the sixth hypothesis in this research.

In research by Ekawati et al. (2019), it is said that if all members of the organization work following the guidelines to create an organizational culture that depends on Allah SWT with absolute commitment and sincerity, it is hoped that Allah SWT will be pleased, which will lead to organizational success in the form of better productivity. Based on this description, the results follow the results of research conducted by Ekawati et al. (2019) and Paais & Pattiruhu (2020).

H7: The Effect of Strategic Planning on Company Performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.376 in strategic planning to company performance. This means a relationship exists between the strategic plan variable and the company's performance variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is 3.787 and the p values are 0.000 (<0.05), which means that strategic planning is directly related to company performance. Based on this description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Natasha & Devie (2013) and Suwono (2018).

H8: Effect of External Environmental Factors on Company Performance Mediated by Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, external environmental variables affect organizational performance, with strategic planning acting as a mediator between the two. The original sample number from the relationship to the three variables is 0.176 which means that there is a positive influence in the relationship of the external environment on the company's performance and strategic plans as a mediator. Then, the number of t statistics is 2,586 include values of 0,010(< 0.05), which means that the external environmental factor variables are indirectly related to organizational performance and strategic planning, which acts as a mediator.

A balanced corporate environment results in the need for organizations to formulate strategic plans. In preparing a strategic plan, the managers need to see and design the company's internal and external environmental factors. These conditions and factors influence each other during the decision-making cycle in strategic planning and policies to manage the company so as to produce the

desired organizational performance. Based on the description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Mardiyono (2013).

H9: Effect of Managerial Factors on Company Performance Mediated by Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, management variables have an effect on organizational performance, with strategic plans acting as mediators between the two. The original sample number from the relationship to the three variables is 0,070 which means there is a positive influence in managerial influence on organizational performance with strategic plans as mediators. Then, the number of t statistics is 2,136 as well as a p value worth 0.033 (< 0.05) which means that managerial factor variables are indirectly related to company performance with strategic planning acting as a mediator.

Factors of managerial expertise in strategic plans are needed to improve performance and competitiveness; if managers do not have expertise in formulating strategic plans, the company will find it difficult to develop and adapt to a dynamic environment. (Meliala et al., 2020). Based on the description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Adriana et al. (2014) and Meliala et al. (2020).

H10: The Influence of Corporate Culture on Company Performance Mediated by Strategic Planning

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, the variable of company behavior on company performance with strategic planning acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample number from the relationship to the three variables is 0.128 it means that there is a relationship in the influence of company behavior on company performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the value of t statistic is 2,379 include a value worth 0.018 (< 0.05) means that the corporate culture variable is indirectly related to the company's performance with strategic planning that acts as a mediator.

A good corporate culture in the company will able to improve the company's performance, especially when juxtaposed with strategic planning. This will encourage managers to carry out their work in a more structured and programmed manner so that it can directly improve the company's performance. Based on this description, the research results are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Mediaty (2010).

4. Conclusion

According to this research, the following conclusions can be drawn according to the previous chapter:

1. Based on the statistical analysis of the patch coefficient in the patch coefficient table, the original sample value is 0.468 on external environmental factors to the strategic plan. This shows that there is a relationship between the external environment variable and the strategic plan variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 4,256 and the p-value is big as 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that external environmental factors are directly related to strategic planning.

2. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table, the original sample value is 0.185 on managerial factors to strategic plans. This shows that there is a relationship between managerial variables and strategic planning variables. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 2,366 and p values big as 0.018 (<0.05) mean that managerial factors are directly related to strategic planning.
3. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table, it shows the original sample value of 0.341 on organizational culture to strategic planning. This shows that there is a relationship between the company's habit variable and the strategic planning variable. Instead of that, it is also shown that the t-statistical figure is equivalent 3,003 and a p-value of 0.003 (< 0.05) which means that culture has a significant direct effect on strategic planning.
4. The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.233 on external environmental factors to the company's performance. This shows that there is a relationship between the external environmental variables and the company's performance variables. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 2,276 and the p-value is as big as 0.023 (< 0.05), which means that external environmental factors are directly related to the company's performance.
5. The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.103 on managerial factors to company performance. This shows that there is a relationship between managerial factor variables and company performance variables. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 2,050 and the p-value big as 0.029 (<0.05), which means managerial factors are directly related to company performance.
6. The statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table shows the original sample value of 0.285 on organizational culture to company performance. This shows that there is a relationship between organizational habits variables and company performance variables. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 2,780 and the p-value as big as 0.006 (< 0.05), which means that organizational culture is directly related to organizational performance.
7. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficients in the path coefficient table, it shows the original sample value of 0.376 on strategic planning to company performance. This shows that there is a relationship between the strategic plan variable and the organizational performance variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t statistic is equivalent 3,787 and the p value is big as 0.000 (<0.05), which means that strategic planning is directly related to the company's performance.
8. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, external environmental variables affect organizational performance, with strategic planning acting as a mediator. The original sample numbers for these three variables are 0.176 which means that there is a positive influence in the relationship of the external environment on organizational performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the number t statistic is equal to 2,586, and the p-value is as big as 0.010 (< 0.05) which means that the external environmental factor variables are indirectly related to the company's performance with strategic planning acting as a mediator.
9. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, managerial variables affect organizational performance and strategic plans that act as mediators. The original sample numbers for these three variables are 0.070 which means that there is a positive influence in managerial influence on organizational performance and strategic plans become a mediator. Then, the t statistic is worth 2,136 and p-value is 0.033 (<0.05) which means that managerial factor

variables are not related to company performance and strategic planning, which acts as a mediator.

10. Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the indirect effect table, the company's customs on company performance with strategic planning act as mediators. The original sample numbers for these three variables are 0.128 means there is a relationship between company habits with company performance with strategic planning as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2,379 and the p-value is 0.018 (< 0.05) means that the cultural variable is indirectly related to the company's performance with strategic planning that acts as a mediator.

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